

Evaluative Research of the Implemented Senior High School Curriculum in a Private University

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Abstract— This study focused on providing facts and information derived from the issue of curriculum implementation among teachers in the senior high school program and providing information on its evaluation. The study analyzed various curriculum interpretations and experiences among the respondents. Teachers' gender, professional qualification, teaching experience, and relevant trainings attended related to the curriculum was examined. The study evaluated the extent of respondents' knowledge if they emphasize essential skills and knowledge required, the awareness on their role as educators, their attitudes in the implementation process, and the extent of their beliefs about the abilities of their students to succeed in work and life, and their self-confidence regarding their classroom practice. Furthermore, this study compared and correlated the critical variables in the study and determined if some variables exhibited main effect with each other. Lastly, it evaluated the internal and external support factors in the curriculum implementation. Results of evaluation showed that respondents exhibited a high level of knowledge, awareness, and belief. A fairly positive attitude towards the implementation process was shown. Also, a high level of confidence in the implementation was manifested. There was a high level of internal support factors while a moderate level of external support was perceived. Results showed that gender, professional qualifications, years as a teacher, and seminars affects the implementation process. This study discusses the implications of the findings on how teaching of the curriculum is conducted in a classroom level environment of a private institution. The study also provides recommendations for considerations.

Keywords— *Implementation, Evaluation, Senior high school curriculum*

I. INTRODUCTION

Former President Benigno Simeon Aquino III signed into law on May 15, 2013 the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 or commonly known as the K-12 program. It was enacted because the Philippines is the very last country in Asia and one of only three countries worldwide with a 10-year pre-university cycle (Acosta, 2016). Presently, the Department of Education (DepEd) is using the K-6-4-2 Model. This model involves kindergarten, six years of elementary education, four years of junior high school and two years of senior high school. The additional two years of senior high school (SHS) intend to give time for students to merge acquired academic skills and expertise and will help prepare learners with skills that will better train them for employment, entrepreneurship, skills development, and higher education (Official Gazette, 2013).

Private and public high schools, colleges, universities and technical institutions can offer Senior High School Curriculum. This Basic Education Program is the flagship program of the Department of Education in its desire to offer a curriculum which is accustomed to the P-21 framework (Mohammad, 2016). This Framework describes the skills, knowledge and expertise students must master to be successful in work and life; it is a blend of content knowledge, specific skills, expertise and literacy. Within the context of core knowledge instruction, students must also learn the critical skills for success in today's world, such as critical thinking, problem solving, communication and collaboration (AACTE, 2008). K-12 years of learning will give every student an opportunity to receive quality education that is globally competitive based on the pedagogically sound curriculum that is at par with international standards (*R.A.10533*). The SHS program is relatively new in the Philippines, with the first year enrollees (grade 11) started June 2016. It leads to course of demand for qualified teachers in specialized areas. DepEd law requires teachers in the SHS to be licensed teachers. Since some specialized courses are rare majors in education degrees, the department was unable to fill it up as compulsory. This forced DepEd to allow non-licensed teachers to handle specialized classes and was given five years to get the license. In the tech-voc track, only NC II holders were allowed to teach, some of them are not degree holders. However, they too are required to acquire a license to teach within five years as well (DepEd, 2016). To provide quality education to students, we have to rely much on what teachers can do in the teaching and learning process. With this considerable role of the teachers in our system of education, we should undeniably not leave anything to chance, from the policy making to the implementation; everything should be based from the results of accurately conducted researches (Pilarta, 2015). Teachers must be agents of embedding required knowledge and skills in all subjects in the senior high school curricula in agreement with national basic education standards. Thus, this study was conducted to add knowledge and fill in some of the gaps of the Philippine educational research focused on providing necessary information derived from researches on the concern of curriculum implementation concerning teachers in the senior high school program and providing facts on its evaluation. This paper is an essential step in an attempt to evaluate if necessary knowledge, skills, and expertise required by the present curriculum are being formally achieved by looking into teachers' perceptions based from evaluations. As this study is focused on the evaluation of the implemented Senior High School curriculum, a study conducted by Canezo

in 2016 is related. The objective was to ascertain the awareness, preparedness and needs of the K to 12 Senior High School Modeling Implementation of which SHS students, faculty and school heads served as respondents. He found out that the lead implementers are much aware of the background and rationale of the program. However, it is observed that the program implementers have reasonably felt concerns on the preparedness and needs. The extent of support from the stakeholders is only relatively apparent. Thus, he arrived at the conclusion that there is a need to come up with contingency measures particularly on the advocacy, linkages and partnerships, curriculum development and upgrading, instructional materials development, skills enhancement and provisions of facilities and equipment for laboratory workshops. The mentioned study is related to the present study since it was focused on evaluating the implementation of the curriculum based from teachers' perception. The present study is somewhat different because it was aimed not only on the internal and external support factors but also on the epistemological factors and characteristics of teachers implementing the curriculum both personal and professional. Thus, this paper may provide information on the evaluation if teachers are giving the necessary skills, knowledge, literacy, and expertise aligned to the goals of the curriculum. This study aimed to conduct an evaluative research of the implemented Senior High School Curriculum in a private university.

II. METHODS

This study utilized a quantitative approach. It made use of a survey to gather information on the profile characteristics of respondents, extent of epistemological factors, internal support factor, and external support factor on the implementation of the curriculum and later was described, compared and correlated. The study was conducted at the Senior High School Department of Saint Mary's University during the School Year 2018-2019. The department is already on its third year of implementing the new basic education curriculum as mandated by law. The insights were drawn from the responses to questionnaires to senior high school teacher respondents. Population sampling was used in the study to gather data.

The survey instrument is made up of four sections. Most items of the overall extent of implementation were measured by a 4-point *Likert* scale. A qualitative description was used to classify the mean score of each test. Response options in this study ranged 1 to 4 eliminating the neutral response option to encourage participants to make a decision regarding their thoughts and feelings as opposed to indicating that they had no opinion. Some items were dichotomous type of questions. A reliability test was also conducted. The *Cronbach's alphas* were computed for each of the items on Epistemological Factors, Internal, External factors and Overall Cronbach Alpha for the overall questionnaire. Among the 156 items, *Cronbach's alpha* showed the questionnaire to reach excellent reliability, $\alpha=0.980$. All items appeared worthy of retention, resulting in a decrease in the alpha if deleted.

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used. First, descriptive information on the demographic profile were described using tables with valid frequencies and percentages. Also measures of central tendency (means and standard deviations) were tabulated in describing the data for teacher epistemologies, internal and external school factors and were presented graphically. Second, to determine the difference between and among variables, selected statistics in comparing mean scores were employed using parametric tests. Repeated measures by *Pairwise* comparisons were also performed to help support other inquiries. Third, to determine the relationship between selected or critical variables, nonparametric correlation was utilized. All hypotheses were examined at a minimum of the $p<0.05$ level of significance.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Subjects

There were more female than male respondents. In terms of professional qualification, the majority of the respondents were 4 years education graduate, few were masterate and doctorate degree holder. In the senior high school, non-education graduates were qualified to teach as long as they passed the Licensure Examination or acquire a license to teach within five years. As for the number of years in the teaching profession, most teachers have 3 years and below teaching experience. With respect to the number of years as a teacher in the senior high curriculum, dominantly are respondents having 1 year and below. All respondents have attended relevant seminars related to the curriculum implementation but with varying length of time.

Epistemological Factors of Teachers

Knowledge

The respondents were tasked to rate the extent of their knowledge if they emphasize in their teaching the essential skills, knowledge, expertise and literacy required by the curriculum.

Table 1. Mean and Standard Deviation of Knowledge as Epistemological Factor

ITEMS ON KNOWLEDGE	Mean	SD	QD
On 21st century	3.28	0.46614	High
On Learning and Innovation Skills	3.53	0.57062	Very High Level
On Information, Media and Technology Skills	3.40	0.59205	High Level
On Life and Career Skills	3.32	0.53282	High
OVERALL	3.47	0.52563	High

Legend: Very Low Level (1.00-1.49); Low Level (1.50-2.49); High Level (2.50-3.49); Very High Level (3.50-4.00)

A quick glance at table shows that the respondents manifested a knowledge that they emphasized in their teaching all necessary knowledge and skills on the curriculum to a high

level. Looking closely at the figures though will reveal little disparities in their responses which may not impact on the overall picture of the respondents' knowledge, but still important to point out. Knowledge on Learning and Innovation Skills showed the highest mean interpreted as very high level. *Pairwise* comparisons between and among group show that the highest knowledge that they emphasize is learning and innovation. The other groups showed no significant difference on mean scores. This implies that the teachers in the senior high school department are preparing the students the necessary skills, literacy and knowledge in life and in work.

Awareness

In the senior high school curriculum, educators are expected that they must be aware of their role as teachers. The table below shows the extent of awareness of the respondents on their role as educators in the senior high school curriculum.

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviation of Awareness as Epistemological Factor

Statements	Mean	SD	QD
1. Successfully aligning technologies with content	3.50	0.614	Very High Level
2. Aligning instruction with standards	3.60	0.606	Very High Level
3. Balancing direct instruction strategically	3.38	0.602	High Level
4. Applying child and adolescent development knowledge	3.22	0.648	High Level
5. Using a range of assessment strategies	3.54	0.503	Very High Level
6. Participating actively in learning communities	3.48	0.677	High Level
7. Acting as mentors and peer coaches	3.46	0.676	High Level
8. Using a range of strategies	3.46	0.676	High Level
9. Pursuing continuous learning opportunities	3.58	0.609	Very High
OVERALL	3.468	.5256	High

Legend: Very Low Level (1.00-1.49); Low Level (1.50-2.49); High Level (2.50-3.49); Very High Level (3.50-4.00)

As shown in the table, the respondents generally exhibited a high level of awareness on their role as implementers of the curriculum. What is exciting in the result is that, there were items where in a very high level was obtained. *Pairwise* comparison results show that there are favored roles which exhibited a significant difference when compared with the other groups. The respondents exhibited a higher awareness on some roles compared with the other

groups. These results imply that teachers in the current study suggest that they are highly aware of their role in the implementation of the curriculum. They are expected to model the kinds of teachers that best promote 21st century skills for students and meet the demands of the global economy by exemplifying and embedding in their instruction skills and literacy required by the curriculum.

Attitude

Table 3. Mean and Standard Deviation of Attitude as Epistemological Factor

Statements	Mean	SD	QD
I am satisfied with the senior high school curriculum	2.78	0.764	Fairly Positive
The senior high school curriculum improved me	3.20	0.571	Fairly Positive
The school management is pleased with the curriculum	3.06	0.470	Fairly Positive
Parents of the learners of my class are pleased curriculum	2.90	0.580	Fairly Positive
The curriculum is too demanding in time & energy	3.16	0.955	Fairly Negative
I am insecure about how to implement the curriculum	2.46	0.908	Fairly Positive
As a teacher I have nothing to learn from the curriculum	1.70	0.953	Fairly Positive
I find the curriculum confusing	2.54	0.788	Fairly Negative
I am not committed in teaching the curriculum	1.92	0.986	Fairly Positive
The curriculum clearly explains my expectations	3.02	0.589	Fairly Negative
OVERALL	2.674	.4601	Fairly Positive

Legend: Very Negative (1.00-1.49); Fairly Negative (1.50-2.49); Fairly Positive (2.50-3.49); Very Positive (3.50-4.00)

As gleaned from table 7 the respondents generally have fairly positive attitudes towards the implementation of the curriculum. On the contrary, 3 items reflected a fairly negative attitude. The respondents see the curriculum as too demanding in terms of their time, energy and skills spent on planning and teaching. Furthermore, the curriculum for them is confusing and does not clearly explain their expectations in the classroom situation.

Belief

Table 4. Mean and Standard Deviation of Belief as Epistemological Factor

Skills and Literacy Items	Mean	SD	QD
Global Awareness	3.346	0.534	High Level
Financial, Economic, Business and Entrepreneurial Literacy	3.293	0.561	High Level
Civic Literacy	3.253	0.557	High Level
Health Literacy	3.304	0.533	High Level
Environmental Literacy	3.400	0.454	High Level
Learning and Innovation Skills	3.492	0.496	High Level
Critical Thinking and Problem Solving	3.391	0.453	High Level
Communication and Collaboration	3.458	0.515	High Level
Information, Media and Technology Skills	3.456	0.517	High Level
Media Literacy	3.472	0.491	High Level
ICT Literacy	3.533	0.508	Very High Level
Life and Career Skills	3.468	0.489	High Level
Initiative and Self-Direction	3.400	0.538	High Level
Social and Cross-Cultural Skills	3.512	0.534	Very High Level
Production and Accountability	3.380	0.598	High Level
Leadership and Responsibility	3.360	0.578	High Level
OVERALL	3.407	0.443	High Level

Legend: Very Low Level (1.00-1.49); Low Level (1.50-2.49); High Level (2.50-3.49); Very High Level (3.50-4.00)

The table above shows that teachers exhibited a high level of belief that students completing the senior high school curriculum are likely to succeed in work and life in the 21st century. There are three favored groups which are significantly higher than the other groups. The researchers showed the highest belief that after completing the curriculum the students are likely to have Learning and Innovation Skills, ICT (Information, Communications and Technology) skills, and Social and Cross-Cultural Skills

Behavior

Table 5. Mean and Standard Deviation of Behavior as Epistemological Factor

SECTIONS Statements	Mean	SD	QD
I was not trained for the	1.62	0.805	High
I am not teaching at the grade level of my training	1.58	0.609	High Level
I am not teaching my subject	1.42	0.702	Very High
I lack confidence in my	1.42	0.609	Very High
OVERALL	1.51	0.497	High

Legend: Very High Level (1.00-1.49); High Level (1.50-2.49); Low Level (2.50-3.49); Very Low Level (3.50-4.00)

As can be seen in table 9, the respondents generally exhibited a high level of response on the statements related to self confidence or efficacy/ behavior regarding the implemented curriculum. It implies that a very high level of self efficacy and confidence were exhibited by the respondents because they were teaching and were trained on the subject of their expertise or specialization.

Interaction Effect Test

A statistical test was conducted if there is an effect of professional qualifications and number of seminars attended related to senior high school on the knowledge, awareness, attitudes, belief and self-efficacy of the respondents. The tables below show the result of the statistics.

A. Effect of Professional Qualifications and Trainings to Knowledge

Table 6. Result of Factorial Analysis of Variance for Knowledge

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects					
Dependent Variable: MEANKNOWLEDGE					
Source	Type III	df	Mean	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	4.511 ^a	11	.410	2.068	.048
Intercept	192.931	1	192.931	973.130	.000
PQ	1.298	3	.433	2.183	.106
SEM	.383	3	.128	.643	.592
PQ * SEM	2.553	5	.511	2.575	.042

*significant at 0.05 level

There is a significant interaction effect of professional qualification and trainings on the knowledge (p=0.042) of the respondents regarding on how and what they emphasized in their teaching. No decision for the main effect of number of seminars attended (p=0.592), and on the main effect of professional qualification (p=0.106). There are groups which have significantly different mean on knowledge. Descriptive statistics shows that the group of respondents, who are 4 year education graduate with 9-16 hours attended trainings, masterate degree holder with 8 hours and below and 9-16 hours attended trainings had the highest knowledge that they are emphasizing the necessary skills on the curriculum based on their mean knowledge. Those who are 4 year non education graduate with 24 hours and above attended trainings had the lowest mean in terms of knowledge that they teach the required skills, knowledge and expertise by the curriculum.

B. Effect of Professional Qualifications and Trainings to Awareness

Table 7. Result of Factorial Analysis of Variance for Awareness

Source	Type III	df	Mean	F	Sig.
Corrected	6.109 ^a	11	.555	2.841	.008
Intercept	202.712	1	202.712	1036.879	.000
PQ	1.728	3	.576	2.946	.045
SEM	.846	3	.282	1.442	.246
PQ * SEM	3.558	5	.712	3.640	.009

*significant at 0.05 level

There is a significant interaction effect of professional qualification and trainings on the awareness of the respondents regarding on their role as educators. No decision for the main effect of number of seminars attended, and on the main effect of professional qualification. There are groups which have significantly different mean in terms of awareness. Descriptive statistics suggests that the group of respondents, who are 4 year education graduate with 9-16 hours attended trainings, masterate degree holder with 24 hours and above and doctorate with 8 hours and below who attended trainings had the highest awareness on their role. Those who are 4 year non education graduate with 24 hours and above attended trainings had the lowest mean in terms of awareness of their role as implementer.

C. Effect of Professional Qualifications and Trainings in terms of Attitudes

Table 8. Result of Factorial Analysis of Variance for Attitudes

Source	Type III	df	Mean	F	Sig.
Corrected	6.492 ^a	11	.590	5.774	.000
Intercept	115.935	1	115.935	1134.225	.000
PQ	1.156	3	.385	3.771	.018
SEM	.534	3	.178	1.741	.175
PQ *	3.033	5	.607	5.934	.000

*significant at 0.05 level

There is a significant interaction effect of professional qualification and trainings on the attitudes of the respondents towards the implementation of the program. No decision for the main effect of number of seminars attended, and on the main effect of professional qualification. There are groups which have significantly different mean in terms of attitudes. Descriptive statistics suggests that the group of respondents, who are 4 year education graduate with 9-16 hours attended trainings, had the highest attitude towards the implementation of the senior high school program. Those who are 4 year non-education graduate with 24 hours and above attended trainings and masterate with 8 hours and below had the lowest mean in terms of attitude.

C. Effect of Professional Qualifications and Trainings in terms of Belief

Table 9. Result of Factorial Analysis of Variance for Belief

Source	Type III Sum	df	Mean	F	Sig.
Corrected	5.142 ^a	11	.467	3.945	.001
Intercept	188.000	1	188.000	1586.725	.000
PQ	1.279	3	.426	3.598	.022
SEM	.620	3	.207	1.745	.174
PQ * SEM	3.049	5	.610	5.147	.001

*significant at 0.05 level

There is a significant interaction effect of professional qualification and trainings on the belief of the respondents regarding on the readiness of the students to succeed in work and life in the 21st century. No decision for the main effect of number of seminars attended, and on the main effect of professional qualification. There are groups which have significantly different mean in terms of their belief. Descriptive statistics suggests that the group of respondents, who are 4 year education graduate with 9-16 hours attended trainings and masterate degree with 24 hours and above attended trainings had the highest belief. Those who are 4 year non-education graduate with 24 hours and above attended trainings had the lowest mean in terms of belief.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The first main objective underlying the current study was to determine the teachers' demographical variables. The large number of teachers in this study with less than three years of teaching experience and having few numbers with graduate school qualifications were found as an issue of major concern. It can be concluded that this situation may have a negative impact on the implementation of senior high school curriculum particularly in the critical variables of this study. Measures are therefore required to improve the recruitment and deployment of qualified teachers to teach at the senior high school. The second objective was to determine the epistemological factors of the respondents. The little disparity of results but significantly different among the factors on knowledge and belief can be a basis for the school administration to further check the other skills and expertise if given emphasis in the implementation process using assessments. Because awareness

and attitudes and behaviors are regarded as individual's affective and evaluative response to something, it is the view of the researcher that perhaps efforts to provide professional development programs to empower teachers with the necessary awareness on their roles and their attitudes for a more effective implementation of the curriculum. Students may not master 21st century skills without the support of teachers who are well trained and supported in this type of instruction. 21st century professional development opportunities may prepare educators to integrate 21st century skills into learning standards and classroom instruction. The findings suggest that continuous professional development like trainings/seminars and attending graduate studies has an effect on the extent to which teachers implement a curriculum innovation. It could thus be concluded from the findings of this study that relevant and specific professional development programs aimed at empowering teachers' knowledge, awareness, attitudes, and belief can positively affect the implementation of the curriculum. It can also be concluded that the encouragement of stakeholders as partners and to support educational initiatives are significant in preparing students in the 21st century. Stakeholders play a key role in the planning and design processes of the curriculum policy, many of the stakeholders remain unsupportive in the implementation process of the curriculum based from the result of this study. It therefore recommended that policy makers should continue to promote the plurality of agents for the benefit of teachers and learners at the classroom level. It can be concluded based from the results of inferential tests that professional qualifications and number of relevant trainings can have an interaction effect and correlation on the epistemological factors in implementing the curriculum. This

therefore, means that internal and external support factors in the implementation process must be given emphasis.

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